

UREA DOPED LEAD ACETATE CRYSTAL FOR OPTO-ELECTRONIC AND PHOTONIC APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Single crystals of leadacetate doped urea an organic nonlinear optical material was grown by slow evaporation solution growth technique. Many interesting results on several properties of leadacetate impurity added to urea single crystal have been observed and studied. The different morphology of lead acetate doped urea crystal was noticed. The presence of functional group has been estimated by FTIR analysis. The lattice parameters of the grown crystals were studied by single crystal X-ray diffraction technique showing a slight modification than urea. Powder X-ray diffraction studies confirm the diffraction planes of grown crystal. The effectiveness of different impurities in changing the surface morphology is different has been reported by SEM and EDS graph confirms the presence of Pb(II) in the crystalline matrix. Optical study implies that so grown lead acetate doped urea crystal is suitable for opto-electronic devices and photonic applications. Thermal studies confirms the crystallinity, decomposition point and thermal stability of the grown crystal.

Keywords: crystal, FTIR, Single crystal XRD, Powder XRD, SEM and EDS.

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Introduction

Non linear Optic (NLO) materials showing second harmonic generation have been in demand over the last few decades due to technological importance in fields of optical communication signal processing and instrumentation¹⁻³. Urea being a NLO material its

crystallization and handling is rather difficult as it is highly hygroscopic. Different derivatives of urea have been studied for NLO applications, some of them are found useful for NLO applications⁴.⁵. Urea crystals fascinate the attention of both theoreticians and experimentalist due to the non linear optical piezoelectric properties. Urea is applicable to photonics and reference material in the DMOS (Diffusive mixing of organic solution experiment in microgravity carried out by NASA. Urea and urea derivatives thiourea, N'N dimethyl urea have been tried as a dopant in KDP.⁶⁻⁹ Investigations on SHG, laser induced damage, thermal properties, influence of pH on morphology, optical properties and growth rate of urea crystals have been reported. The effect of doping on the properties of urea has been extensively studied. Recently synthetic growth of semiorganic TGDCC (Tetra glycindihydrated calcium chloride) single crystal and a study of effect by urea on the structural and optical properties¹⁰ were studied. Optical and thermal studies on pure and doped L – arginine phosphate crystals¹¹, urea oxalic acid crystals¹², KDP crystals¹³ were studied. Characterisation studies of urea induced ammonium nickel sulfate hexahydrate¹⁴ and comparative study of pure and urea doped glycine phosphite crystals¹⁵, sulphamic acid single crystals¹⁶, were studied. Growth and analysis of urea thiourea sodium sulphate crystal¹⁷ were studied. Bismuth fluoride introduced into the Urea crystals to alter the various properties, bismuth fluoride is the p-block element and if it is doped into the organic crystals like Urea, NLO properties of host material will be improved¹⁸. In this paper leadacetate doped urea crystal was grown by slow evaporation solution method for the first time and the results of various studies FTIR, thermal, single crystal XRD, powder XRD of the grown crystals are reported.

Crystal growth

Crystal growth of lead acetate doped urea was done by taking both mixture (equimolar) in 1:1 ratio by slow evaporation solution growth technique at room temperature using triply distilled water as solvent. The mixture of lead acetate and urea was taken in a conical flask with triply distilled water as solvent, the contents in the conical flask was stirred for 3hrs, forming colourless

precipitate which was then filtered in a beaker and the filtrate is covered with polythene sheet provided with holes, the precipitate was kept aside. The filtrate in beaker was maintained in room temperature condition for 25 – 30 days, at 15th day seed crystals were found, in 18th day fluctuate structure is formed and 18th day bulk crystals were found and they were harvested. The 18th day bulk crystals which was clear in growth medium and their image is shown in Figure .1.

Figure.1 Images of (a) lead acetate doped urea crystals.

Fourier Transform Infra Red Analysis

The Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) investigations are carried out on the powdered samples of urea doped ferrous sulphate crystal is given in figure. 2. The growth frequency region is located below 4000 to 1300 cm^{-1} and the fingerprint region 1300 to 700 cm^{-1} . In the FTIR spectrum of urea doped leadacetate crystal figure. 2 a multiple broad band at 3423.6 cm^{-1} and 3261.4 cm^{-1} indicates N-H stretching vibration. A small short peak at 2378 cm^{-1} is caused by asymmetric vibration of gaseous carbondioxide molecule present in the ambient air. The sharp peak at 1628.8 cm^{-1} is

assigned to C-N stretching vibration, at 1449.9cm^{-1} , 1287.8cm^{-1} and 1399.6cm^{-1} is due to bending vibration of C-N-C group. The symmetrical C-C stretching is found to be at 1103.3 , 918.8cm^{-1} . A short peak at 1735.1cm^{-1} is an indicator of photo-oxidation, the material breaking down and forming new carbonyl by products due to environmental stress.

Figure 2 FTIR spectra of leadacetate doped urea crystal

UV-Visible Spectra

UV-Visible spectra in the spectral range of 200-800nm for urea doped leadacetate crystals absorbance graphs are shown in Figure. 3. In the absorbance graph of urea doped leadacetate crystal the spectrum shows low absorbance in the entire visible region, the UV cut-off wavelength is found to be 230nm proving synthesized crystal's higher optical quality inducing both optoelectronic and photonic applications.

The band gap energy for urea doped leadacetate crystal is calculated as 5.40ev by using the formulae, $E_g = hc / \lambda_{\max}$

Where, h –Planck constant, c – Velocity of light, λ_{\max} = Maximum wavelength.

Figure 3 UV-Visible spectra of lead acetate doped urea crystal

Table.1 Band gap energy

System	Band gap energy (Eg) eV
Pure Urea	5.07
Urea/ lead acetate	5.40

Powder X-Ray Diffraction studies

Powder X - ray diffraction analysis of urea doped ferrous sulphate and urea doped leadacetate crystals were performed with a graphite monochromated $CuK\alpha$ radiation and respective XRD patterns are given in the figure.4. The urea doped leadacetate crystal gives high crystallinity with increase in their relative intensities of the peaks particularly at 24.320° and they are shifted to higher counts due to the higher incorporation of dopant leadacetate to urea crystalline matrix. The minute changes in the peak intensities, peak shifts in the observed XRD graph could be attributed to the strain developed by the incorporation of the dopants to urea crystalline matrix.

The particle size of the crystal is calculated due to doping by using scherrer equation:

$$t = K\lambda/(\beta\cos\theta)$$

Where: t- Averaged dimension of crystallites,

k - Scherer constant, (it is usually assumed to be 1)

λ - Wave length of X- ray,

Θ - Peak position measured in radian,

β - Integral breadth of reflection (in radian 2Θ) located at 2Θ .

The particle size of the crystal is calculated due to doping by using scherrer equation as 15.75nm

Figure 4 Powder XRD of urea doped lead acetate crystal

Thermo gravimetric analysis (TGDSC)

The thermogravimetric and differential scanning calorimetry curve of urea doped lead acetate crystal which characterizes its thermal stability, phase transitions and decomposition behaviour is given in figure.5. In TG curve there is no significant weight loss till 80^o a gradual weight loss takes place as the complex structure decomposes. DSC curve shows a broad endothermic peak at around 75^oC, lacks water of crystallization and a sharp endothermic peak at 220^oC corresponding to the melting point of the crystal, volatalization and decomposition of formed crystal. Thus it can be used in photonic industry.

Figure.5 TG-DSC curve of urea doped lead acetate crystal

Scanning electron microscopy- Energy dispersive spectroscopy (SEM-EDS)

For urea doped leadacetate crystal the surface morphology is dendritic with cracks and voids with roughness by doping as shown in the specimens differing their magnifications say 1000 magnification, larger dendritic like morphology in 5000 magnification both with highest surface roughness by doping could be bunched steps or macro steps as shown in the specimens of Figure.5.

The presence of dopant metal lead presence in the doped specimen was confirmed by EDS graph as shown in Figure. 6.

(i) 1000 Magnification

(ii) 5000 Magnification

Figure 5. SEM Image of urea doped lead acetate crystal

Figure .6 EDS graph of urea doped lead acetate crystal

Table.2 Mass and Atomic percentage of urea doped lead acetate crystal

Element	Line	Mass%	Atom%
C	K	20.51±0.54	27.36±0.73
N	K	13.32±0.68	15.23±0.78
O	K	48.64±1.05	48.71±1.05
P	K	16.70±0.37	8.64±0.19
Pb	M	0.83±0.20	0.06±0.02
Total		100.00	100.00
Spc_001			Fitting ratio 0.1582

Table.2 gives the detailed atomic and mass percentage of different components present and the doped impurities actual percentage also confirms the presence of lead, carbon, oxygen, nitrogen, sulphur in the crystalline matrix.

SINGLE CRYSTAL XRD ANALYSIS

The Single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis is done by Bruker AXS (Kappa Apex II) X-ray diffractometer. Here the unit cell values of urea pure, urea doped ferrous sulphate and urea doped leadacetate are determined. The table 3. shows the unit cell values of both urea pure, urea doped. The cell parameter values are increased than urea cell values due to the change in occupational sites of the metal Pb of leadacetate in Urea matrix with cell parameter values $a=7.500\text{Å}$, $b=7.500\text{Å}$, $c=7.549\text{Å}$ and $v=867\text{Å}^3$ with tetragonal system and angles $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90^\circ$ differing from urea forming colourless transparent bulky crystal.

Table-3. Cell parameters values of Urea pure and Urea Ferrous Sulphate crystals.

Lattice Parameter Values	a_A^0	b_A^0	c_A^0	v_A^{03}	System/space group/Beta angle
Urea	5.589	5.589	4.695	146.65	Tetragonal/P42 ₁ m/ 90 ⁰
Urea doped leadacetate	7.500	7.500	7.549	867	Tetragonal/I/ 90 ⁰

Conclusion

Colourless transparent crystals of leadacetate doped urea having reasonably good crystalline quality have been grown by solution growth technique taking triply distilled water as solvent at room temperature. The XRD, FT-IR, thermal studies, SEM-EDS, UV growth techniques have been used to study the influence of lead acetate doping on urea crystal. Incorporation of lead metal of lead acetate in the crystalline matrix of urea is well established by EDS graph. The powder XRD and FT-IR studies reveal that the doping causes a small change in intensity and vibrational patterns, respectively and the particle size of the dopant is calculated by Scherer equation as 15.75 nm. Structural studies indicate that the crystal is under stress and an increase in granularity is observed as a result of doping. SEM image shows dendritic with cracks and voids with roughness morphology in different magnification both with highest surface roughness by doping could be bunched steps or as shown in the image. Optical studies reveals that the UV- Visible has absorbed in lower cutoff to increased wavelength as a result higher band gap energies calculated as 5.40eV implying that the leadacetate doped urea specimen could be applied in the optical windows, laser application and photonics industry. Thermogravimetric and differential scanning calorimetry curve of urea doped lead acetate crystal characterizes its thermal stability, phase transitions and decomposition stating that it can be used in photonic industry.

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